

RAFT (CO)POLYMERIZATION OF CARBAZOLE-CONTAINING STYRENE MONOMERS OF ELECTRON-DONOR AND ELECTRON-ACCEPTOR TYPES

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Thermally activated delayed fluorescent (TADF) materials have received increasing attention as effective emitters for producing highly efficient and low-cost organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) since they exhibit various advantages such as heavy-metal-free structures and 100% theoretical internal quantum efficiency [1]. TADF properties have been transferred from small molecules [2] to polymers [3], however, up to now, only a few studies on TADF polymer emitters have been reported.

Herein we report the reversible addition-fragmentation chain-transfer (RAFT) (co)polymerization of carbazole-containing styrene derivatives, 9-(4-vinylphenyl)carbazole (M1) and 9-(2,3,5,6-tetrafluoro-4-vinylphenyl)carbazole (M2) (Scheme 1) initiated by 2-(dodecylthiocarbonothioylthio)-2-methylpropionic acid (DDAT)/azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) system in 1,4-dioxane (DO) at 70 °C for the first time.

Fig. 1. Scheme of RAFT (co)polymerization of carbazole-containing styrene derivatives.

Polymerization of both monomers proceeds smoothly in a controlled fashion to afford polymers with close to theoretical values of molecular weight. In addition, polymers were characterized by narrow molecular weight distribution ($M_w/M_n=1.16$). The obtained (co)polymers were also characterized via NMR spectroscopy, size exclusion chromatography, differential scanning calorimetry, UV and fluorescence spectroscopies.

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References

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